

Kinetics of Decarboxylation of Malonic Acid in Alcohols and Glycols

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Kinetics of decarboxylation of malonic acid have been studied in alcohols and glycols. The results indicate a solvent-assisted, rate-determining heterolysis of carbon-carbon bond. The nucleophilicity of solvents seems to determine the efficacy of this assistance and hence the rate constants. The rate constants and activation energies are analysed in the light of polar and steric factors operative in the solvents. A discussion attempting to identify the centre of attack in the malonic acid molecule by the solvent species has also been included

DECARBOXYLATIONS are highly sensitive to the nature of solvents in which these reactions are effected¹. In this communication, the effect of alcohols and glycols on the decarboxylation of malonic acid is discussed.

Experimental

Malonic acid (B. D. H.) was recrystallised repeatedly from benzene-ether containing 5% light petroleum and found to be 100% pure (m.p. 135.2°). Ethylene glycol and propylene glycol were dried over sodium sulphate and fractionally distilled. n-Heptanol and n-octanol (commercial) were refluxed with CaO, decanted and distilled.

The decarboxylation was followed manometrically by measuring the volume of carbon dioxide evolved at various intervals of time. The experimental set-up was similar to that devised by Clark².

Results and Discussion

The solvents used are not basic enough to abstract the proton of the substrate to lead to any significant formation of the anion. It has been established that the decarboxylation of malonic acid proceeds by a mechanism essentially different from that of the trihaloacetic acids; the transition state of the decarboxylation of malonic acid involves a cyclic form of the molecule in which one of the carboxyl hydrogen atoms is hydrogen bonded to the carbonyl oxygen of the other acid function ready to switch bonds and lead, as the carbon dioxide moiety leaves to the formation of a 'diol' as the intermediate precursor of the final product³.

Solvent species with favourable electron disposition may aid the reaction by facilitating the slow step, which involves the shift of bonds in the cyclic transition state. This is effected by the solvent molecule employing a lone-pair of electrons on a suitable nucleophilic atom in it, 'releasing' electron-density towards a suitable electrophilic centre in the substrate molecule to form a loose activated complex, which then undergoes reaction,

where S is solvent molecule. In the decarboxylation of malonic acid in dioxane containing small amounts of quinoline, the rate of reaction is proportional to the concentration of quinoline⁴. This proves that the reaction is bimolecular. The formation of the activated complex 3 with a solvent like quinoline lowers the energetic requirements, thereby enhancing the reaction rate when compared to the 'idealised' unimolecular transition state (1), where no external species participates. Obviously the degree to which such energetic favouring of the reaction takes place depends on the effective nucleophilicity of the solvent molecule; the greater its nucleophilicity, the larger is the degree of lowering of energy requirements and faster the rate and vice versa. This lowering of energy requirements will reflect in reduced activation energy for the reaction.

A solvent which has nucleophilic atom(s) has inherent basic properties in the Lewis sense. The essential factor operating in the decarboxylation is that the solvent must be nucleophilic (basic) enough to coordinate with a suitable electrophilic centre in the substrate molecule, but not nucleophilic (basic) enough to ionise the carboxyl hydrogen of the acid. This notion first suggested for malonic acid decar-

boxylation by Fraenkel *et al.*⁴ has been amply substantiated by extensive series of investigations, undertaken by Clark, of the kinetics of decarboxylation of malonic acid and related compounds in various solvents⁵.

Here, a point of importance is the identity of the nucleophilic centre in the acid species at which coordination with the solvent molecule can take place. A study of the polar factors operating in malonic acid would help to answer this point: the two carbon atoms of the two carboxyl groups are centres of comparatively low electron-density, because the carbonyl polarisation would deprive them of part of their electron density. The $-I_s$ effect of the hydroxyl¹-functions attached to the carbon atoms would tend to decrease the electron-densities further:

Thus there are two carbon atoms of comparatively low electron-density. When the cyclic transition state is visualised, the moot question arises as to which of the two carbon atoms is involved in the formation of the activated complex with solvent molecule. Naturally it should be in the direction in which further reaction is energetically favoured. Of the two possibilities,

5 has to be preferred as in the subsequent course of the shift of bonds, it is C_1 which leaves as CO_2 , it is this centre at which coordination by the solvent molecule rather than at C_3 would facilitate the reaction to a greater extent. This does not preclude the possibility of coordination at C_3 as well, but just that the activated complex formed involving C_1 as the centre towards which the pair of electrons from the solvent are released is more in concomitance with the energetic requirements of the reaction. Furthermore, such coordination at C_1 would be more in line with another favourable aspect, viz. that it is the C_1 atom which is subsequently lost as CO_2 and with a solvent molecule 'solvating' it thereby aiding its removal, may work towards that direction.

A measure of the relative nucleophilicities of various molecules may be obtained by molecular orbital methods. In spite of various approxima-

tions that may be employed, the calculations become tedious for heteroatom-containing molecules⁶. One has, therefore, to rely on the relative nucleophilicities of various solvent species as would be predictable on the basis of more classical aspects as the inductive and mesomeric factors operative in the molecule along with any steric factors. The results of the present investigation may be interpreted in the light of polar and steric factors to check whether they add more evidence to the mechanism of decarboxylation.

Reaction in alcohols: The decarboxylation of malonic acid has been studied in n-heptanol and n-octanol. The reaction is found to follow first order kinetics. The rate constants obtained at various temperatures in these two solvents are given in Table 1. The activation parameters are summarised in Table 2. The corresponding values for the reaction in water, n-butanol, n-amyl alcohol and n-hexanol from the literature⁷ are also included in Table 2.

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID IN ALKANOLS

Solvent	Temp. °C	k_1 $\times 10^4, s^{-1}$
n-Heptanol	110.0	2.65
	113.2	3.61
	120.7	6.70
	125.0	9.79
n-Octanol	110.0	2.90
	113.2	4.15
	120.7	7.37
	125.0	10.80

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID IN WATER AND ALKANOLS

Solvent	k_1^* $\times 10^4, s^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
Water	1.75	126	12.7	127
n-Butanol	11.60	114	18.4	121
n-Amyl alcohol	10.20	109	31.8	122
n-Hexanol	10.20	109	31.8	122
n-Heptanol	9.79	108	34.7	122
n-Octanol	10.80	107	37.3	122

*At 125°.

At 125°, the rate constant in n-octanol is slightly higher than that in n-heptanol. However, these values are of the same order as those in other alcohols indicating that the reaction follows the same trend in these related solvents.

Comparing the ΔH^\ddagger values, the trend is obvious though the absolute values do not differ appreciably. The introduction of a methyl group to the sixth carbon atom of a C_8 -chain would not change the inductive effect felt at C_1 appreciably, for, inductive effect falls off rapidly beyond third or fourth carbon atom. Thus, the effective negative charge on the oxygen of the three alcohols, namely n-hexanol, n-heptanol and n-octanol would not differ by any

significant extent or their attraction for the electrophilic centre of malonic acid would be the same. Therefore the ΔH^\ddagger for the reaction in these three solvents should be more or less the same which is actually so, as they differ only by two units.

Considering the ΔS^\ddagger values, the increased carbon-chain length on passing from n-amyl alcohol to n-hexanol does not seem to affect these values. The addition of methyl group to C_5 -atom of n-amyl alcohol does not incur any additional steric interaction when the OH group at C_1 is involved in the formation of the activated complex. But there is regular decrease in ΔS^\ddagger when passing from n-hexanol to n-octanol through n-heptanol. This may arise due to the whip-like tail of the carbon chain increasing the complexity of the activated state with higher alcohols. The carbon chains in these cases exhibit a steric effect, thereby reducing the entropy. It was noted by Clark⁷ that alcohols exist as clusters or 'supermolecules' built-up of 3-4 molecules and he applied this principle in explaining his results. Normally one should expect that such tendency to associate would decrease with increasing carbon chain length. A comparison of entropy values in n-heptanol and n-octanol with those in lower alcohols indicates that such a tendency not to associate has not yet set-in in heptanol and octanol. For, if in these two alcohols a state has reached where there is no association, then these alcohols interacting with malonic acid will be of monomeric or dimeric units which would increase the entropy value as we pass from n-hexanol.

Comparing with water, the situation is rather similar. There is extensive degree of association in water; water by virtue of possessing two hydrogen atoms to one oxygen atom associates to much greater degree through hydrogen bonding than do the alcohols which have only one hydrogen for each oxygen atom. In all the alcohols, the entropy of activation would suffer two effects compared to that in water. The introduction of bulky alkyl group would lower entropy but the fact that the alcohol 'supermolecules' are smaller clusters than water clusters would tend to nullify this decrease. But these values in alcohols are lower indicating that the over-all steric interaction in these cases is more than that in water.

The rate constants at 125° in the alcohols, n-amyl alcohol to n-octanol do not differ significantly in spite of the change in the carbon chain. The lowering of enthalpy nearly compensates for the disadvantage imposed by steric factor on passing from a simple to a complex solvent molecule. This results in constancy of free energy of activation for the reaction in these solvents.

Reaction in glycols: The decarboxylation has been carried out in two glycols. The rate constants are given in Table 3. In Table 4 are given the Arrhenius parameters for the reaction in glycols; the corresponding values in glycerol⁸ are also included for comparison.

TABLE 3—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID IN GLYCOLS

Solvent	Temp. °C	k_1 $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Ethylene glycol	98.2	0.49
	110.0	1.37
	117.3	2.42
	125.0	4.68
Propylene glycol	99.9	0.58
	110.0	1.42
	113.2	2.12
	125.2	6.12

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID IN GLYCOLS AND GLYCEROL

Solvent	k_1° $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
Ethylene glycol	4.68	102	57.3	125
Propylene glycol	6.12	117	16.3	124
Glycerol	4.79	103	51.1	124

*At 125°

Ethylene glycol may be considered as water molecule in which one hydrogen is replaced by a β -hydroxyethyl group while propylene glycol by a γ -hydroxypropyl group. In both the cases, the hydroxy alkyl groups would inductively withdraw electrons due to the electronegative oxygen (though alkyl groups have + I_s effect, hydroxyl alkyl groups have - I_s effect). This would lead to a decreased attraction between the hydroxylic oxygen of glycols and the polarised carbonyl carbon of malonic acid. Therefore ΔH^\ddagger in glycols must be higher than that in water, but actually they are lower. A plausible but not fully satisfactory explanation may be advanced to explain this result. Water is highly polymerised and it is likely that the flexibility of the electron density on the oxygen atom is decreased due to many hydrogen atoms surrounding it. But with glycol, the degree of polymerisation being less this effect may not arise. Thus the oxygen atom of glycol can be more nucleophilic when compared to the oxygen atom of water with the result that the enthalpy of activation is lower in the former solvent.

The higher value of ΔH^\ddagger in propylene glycol compared to that in ethylene glycol may arise due to the possible fixation of the mobile electron of the oxygen due to internal hydrogen bonding. The methyl group in propylene glycol due to its + I_s effect may favour the internal hydrogen bonding to a greater degree than in ethylene glycol. This behaviour in propylene glycol, tying down the lone-pair of electrons of hydroxyl oxygen atom would require a breakdown of this hydrogen bonded structure before the electrons can be effectively used for interaction with malonic acid.

For the decarboxylation of oxalic acid, Clark observed a much lower value of ΔS^\ddagger (-30.0 e.u.) in ethylene glycol compared to that in 1,3-butanediol (-4.9 e.u.)⁹. He attributed this difference to an extensive linear polymerisation of ethylene glycol

molecule leading to a greater degree of association and hence a larger steric interaction in the formation of transition complex with oxalic acid. The 1,3-glycols on the otherhand, due to intervention of a methylene group have a lesser tendency for association, though internal hydrogen bond is possible. Rather similar arguments can be advanced for the reaction of malonic acid in ethylene and propylene glycols. The ΔS^\ddagger value in ethylene glycol is lower compared to that in propylene glycol indicating again a more complicated 'bulk structure' for the former. The question here is why such a linear polymerisation is prevented or existing to a lesser degree in propylene glycol which is also a 1,2-diol. The reason should lie obviously in the fact that the introduction of a methyl group can sterically hinder polymerisation in propylene glycol. The question of whether any internal hydrogen bonding is obtained in propylene glycol as in the case of butane-1,3-diol has to be settled in terms of relative stabilities of five- and six-membered rings, but that may not account for the observed difference in entropy values. The lower ΔS^\ddagger value in ethylene glycol may arise due to possible 'cage effect', the malonic acid being trapped by two glycol molecules in the transition state. The methyl group in propylene glycol may prevent such cage formation. In any case, the molecular cluster of propylene glycol, which would interact with malonic acid in the formation of the transition state, may be a simpler entity than that of ethylene glycol which accounts for the observed higher entropy in the former solvent.

Again, comparing with water, there is less extensive association for propylene glycol which would increase the entropy, but the large bulk of the monomer itself can decrease it to such a degree that the value becomes lesser to that in water. That is to say that the 'supermolecules' of propylene glycol which interact with malonic acid are on the whole more complicated than those of water.

The activation parameters for the reaction in ethylene glycol and glycerol are very close indicating that the two solvents resemble each other in electrical and structural properties in spite of the presence of three hydroxyl groups in glycerol.

Clark⁵ showed that for the decarboxylation of malonic acid in various solvent, a plot of ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger gives two independent straight lines which are parallel with a slope of 408 K, namely the iso-kinetic temperature. This happens to be the melting point of malonic acid. Based on this, it has been concluded that the solvents used for the reaction can be classified into two categories. Monocarboxylic acids, nitro compounds and phenols fall in one category while alcohols in the other. When the values obtained in the present study are similarly plotted (Fig. 1) it is found that the points corresponding to n-heptanol and n-octanol fall on the line (B) along with other alcohols. The points corresponding to glycols, on the otherhand, constitute a separate straight line (C) with that for glycerol, this line being parallel and

close to the line constituted by simple alcohols. The points corresponding to esters of aromatic acid¹⁰ fall on the line (A) along with carboxylic acids, etc. It is, therefore, evident that the isokinetic temperature principle is obeyed, in these solvents. Being

Fig. 1. The ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger plot for decarboxylation of malonic acid in: (A) esters, (B) alcohols and (C) glycols.

parallel, these three lines have the same slope of 408 K (135°). The values of intercepts which represent the free energy of reaction for lines (B) and (C) are 121.9 and 125.6 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively, which are close to the values given in Table 2 and Table 4 respectively. These observations indicate that the decarboxylation of malonic acid follows the same mechanism in these sets of solvents but the rate of reaction at the isokinetic temperature is different in different sets of solvents.

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